

Molecular characterisation of mtDNA D-loop in three indigenous chicken populations in Southwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

The detailed knowledge of population structure among and within breeds of chickens is essential for conservation and strategies. It is therefore important to evaluate the existing chicken genetic resources using genomic approaches. In most species, the mitochondrial DNA D-loop region is the most variable part of the mitochondrial DNA molecule because of the lack of coding constraints. The analysis of mtDNA D-loop sequences revealed several single nucleotide polymorphisms in the chicken population studied. This study was carried out on indigenous chickens in different geographical zones in South-West region of Nigeria. Nigerian indigenous female chickens consisting of normal feathered (50), frizzle feathered (25) and naked neck (25) constituted base materials for this study, blood samples were collected from the wing veins of each birds and then transferred immediately to FTA card. Following this, the samples were transferred to the ACUTIG Genetics Laboratory, for DNA extraction. Genomic DNA was isolated and amplified with mitochondrial DNA D-loop primers and then sequenced. Data collected were analysed with various molecular software. The calculated Polymorphic information content (PIC) and heterozygosity ranged from 0.43-0.97 and 0.03-0.45 in all the chickens examined with mitochondrial DNA D-loop markers respectively. Single nucleotide polymorphism (SNPs) observed in normal feathered, naked neck and frizzle feathered chickens were 20, 19 and 17 with major allele frequency (MAF) having the lowest and the highest values of 0.55 in SNPs (677A>G) and 0.97 in SNPs (5A>T, 321C>T, 346T>C); 0.64 in SNPs (151T>C, 201C>T, 209C>T, 227C>T, 240C>T, 245T>C, 294T>C, 430T>C, 670A>G) and 0.93 in SNPs (194C>T, 196G>A, 314C>T, 342A>G); and 0.71 in SNPs (677G>A) and 0.93 in SNPs (5A>T) respectively. Networking analysis revealed two haplogroup. The study identified high mtDNA D-loop variation resulting from high mtDNA D-loop polymorphisms in Southwestern Nigeria indigenous chicken populations. Furthermore, the population of indigenous chickens in this study showed low level of heterozygosity and as such may be homogenous in nature which is an indicative of their potentials for genetic improvement via selection or crossbreeding.

Keywords: Nigerian indigenous chicken, polymorphic information content, mitochondrial DNA D-loop, single nucleotide polymorphism, network analysis.

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Introduction

The detailed knowledge of population structure among and within breeds of chickens is essential for conservation and strategies. Therefore, it is necessary to examine the existing chicken genetic resources using genomic approaches. This need to be done for sustainable use of the

existing chicken genotypes that are adapted to the production environment in which they are maintained (Dessie et al., 2011). The genetic diversity and variation can be characterized with various molecular techniques such as microsatellite markers (Oni et al., 2016; Oni et al., 2017 and Adepegba et al., 2021), single

nucleotide polymorphisms (Machete et al., 2021 and Sovi et al., 2024) and mitochondrial DNA D-loop (Okani-Onyejiaka et al., 2022 and Wang et al., 2025). In most species, the mitochondrial DNA D-loop region is the most variable part of the mitochondrial DNA molecule because of the lack of coding constraints (Simon, 1991; Baker and Marshall, 1997). Mitochondrial DNA D-loop sequence has been widely used to study origin, domestication and dispersal of chickens. Studies have shown that mitochondrial DNA D-loop (mtDNA D-loop) high genetic diversity in chicken populations indicates multiple maternal lineages (Okani-Onyejiaka et al., 2022 and Wang et al., 2025).

The analysis of mtDNA D-loop sequences revealed several single nucleotide polymorphisms in the chicken population studied. These single nucleotide polymorphisms can be used to identify haplotypes and haplogroups, which can provide insights into evolutionary history and population dynamics of chicken. The single nucleotide polymorphisms identified in the mtDNA D-loop region can also be used for breed identification, parentage testing and conservation genetics. Therefore, objective of this study was aim at gaining valuable insights into genetic diversity and haplogroup relationship of indigenous chicken populations.

Materials and methods

Experimental location and sampling technique

This study was carried out on indigenous chickens in different geographical zones in South-West region of Nigeria consisting of Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti States located between longitude 2° 3' and 6° 00' east and latitude 6° 21' and 8° 37' north with total

land of 77,818 km² and temperature ranges between 21°C and 30°C while annual rainfall ranges between 1500 mm and 3000 mm (Ajewole, 2005) using judgment sampling method.

Chicken populations, sample size and data collection

Nigerian indigenous female chickens consisting of normal feathered (50), frizzle feathered (25) and naked neck (25) constituted base materials for this study, blood samples (0.5 ml) was collected from the wing veins of each birds using 2 ml disposable syringe and then transferred immediately to FTA® classic card. The samples were taken to the ACUTIG Genetics Laboratory, ACUTIG Nigeria Limited, for DNA extraction.

DNA isolation, quantification and primer selection

Genomic DNA was extracted from air-dried blood spotted on FTA® Classic cards (Whatman BioScience) using tris SDS method of extracting DNA from FTA card. DNA quality was checked by electrophoresis in a min gel and quantified using spectrophotometer (Spectronic® Genesis™) based on absorbance at 260 and 280 nm respectively. The specific primers based on the published mtDNA D-loop gene sequence were selected and used to initiate PCR amplification in a thermal cycler. The primers AV1F2 (Forward sequence (F)) and H547 (Reverse sequence (R)) were used to amplify nine hundred and twenty base pairs (920 bp) of mtDNA D-loop region based on complete chicken mitochondrial genome. The primers type and sequence used in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Sequence primer use for amplification and the sequencing of the segment of mtDNA D-loop gene

Primer type	5' to 3' sequence	Primer name	bp	T _A
mtDNA d-Loop	F (5'-AGGACTACGGCTTGAAAAGC-3')	AV1F2	920	54
	R (5'-ATGTGCCTGACCGAGGAACCAG-3')	H547		

Hassaballah et al. (2015); bp = base pair; T_A= annealing temperature

mtDNA D-Loop PCR programme and conditions

The mtDNA D-loop conditions used with the

final volume of 25 µl included 2.5 µl of 10 x PCR buffer, 2.2 µl of 25 mm/mol MgCl₂, 1 µl of

dNTPs (25 mM dNTPs), 2 µl (1 µl forward plus 1 µl reverse form) of each pair of primer, 0.2 µl *Taq* DNA polymerase (5 U/µl), 16.1 µl autoclave water and 1 µl of template DNA. PCR was performed in thermal cycler (Master cycle Gradient, Eppendorf). The reaction mixture was initial denaturation (96°C, 15 minutes), 40 cycles of denaturation (95°C for 30 seconds), annealing temperature (54°C for 30 seconds) and elongation or extension at 70°C for 1 minute, followed by final extension at 70°C for 5 minutes. The mtDNA D-loop fragments amplified by polymerase chain reaction were separated by 1.5% agarose gel with a drop of (0.5 ul) ethidium bromide used as staining agent. The highly pure and intact DNA (normal feathered = 29, naked neck = 14 and frizzle feathered = 14) of mtDNA D-loop fragments were sequence.

Data analyses

The nucleotide sequences were trimmed and edited using Bioedit (Hall, 1999) and MEGA 6 (Tamura et al., 2013) software were used to remove noises in the sequences. The sequences obtained were aligned with reference (MH_094592). The nucleotide sequences were aligned using Clustal W software implemented in MEGA 6 software. The SNPs present were identified by aligning the sequences with reference using Clustal W (Thompson et al. 1994). The SNPs was confirmed using DNAsp (Librado and Rozas, 2009). The frequency of the SNPs obtained was calculated by dividing frequency of each allele with the total sample size for each genotype.

Heterozygosity of each SNP was determined using the formula below:

$$\text{Heterozygosity (H}_e\text{)} = 1 - (p^2 + q^2) \text{ (Guo and Elston, 1999).}$$

Polymorphic information content (PIC) of the SNPs was calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{PIC} = H_e - 2p^2q^2$$

(Botstein et al., 1980)

Where p is the major allele frequency and q is the minor allele frequency.

The amino acid variation and type of mutation for each SNP was obtained using DNAsp (Librado and Rozas, 2009). Haplotype network was implemented in programme NETWORK 5.1.0.0 (Bandelt *et al.*, 1999).

Results

The single nucleotide polymorphism, heterozygosity, major allele frequency, type of mutation, amino acid variation, polymorphic information content observed in mtDNA D-loop of normal feathered, naked neck and frizzle feathered chickens are depicted in Table 2. Variations in the number of major allele frequency was observed in the normal feathered chicken population studied with the lowest value of 0.55 observed in SNPs (677A>G), while highest value of 0.97 was seen in SNPs (5A>T, 321C>T, 346T>C). The estimates of heterozygosity in the chicken populations ranged from 0.03 in SNPs (5A>T, 321C>T) to 0.45 in SNPs (677A>G). Polymorphic information content (PIC) ranged from 0.43 in SNPs (677A>G) to 0.97 (5A>T, 321C>T). A total number of twenty (20) SNPs were detected in mtDNA D-loop of normal feathered chickens. The normal feathered chicken have nineteen (19) transitions (158T>C, 190T>C, 201C>T, 203G>A, 208C>T, 213A>G, 216C>T, 234C>T, 240A>G, 247C>T, 252T>C, 272A>G, 301T>C, 321C>T, 333A>G, 346T>C, 349A>G, 437T>C and 677A>G) and one (1) transversions (5A>T). Majority of these SNPs had twelve (12) non-synonymous amino acid variations (5A>T, 158T>C, 190T>C, 203G>A, 208C>T, 247C>T, 272A>G, 301T>C, 333A>G, 349A>G, 437T>C and 677A>G), while eight (8) synonymous amino acid variations (201C>T, 213A>G, 216C>T, 234C>T, 240A>G, 252T>C, 321C>T and 346T>C) were detected.

Table 2: Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) identification, major allele frequency (MAF), heterozygosity (H_e), type of mutation, amino acid variation and polymorphic information content (PIC) measured in mtDNA D-loop of normal feathered (Nf), naked neck (Nn) and frizzle feathered (Ff) chickens

G	SNPs	H _e	MAF	Type of mutation	Amino acid variation	Type	PIC
Nf							

5A>T	0.03	0.97	Transversion	Methionine→Alanine	Non-synonymous	0.97
158T>C	0.34	0.65	Transition	Histidine→Cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.55
190T>C	0.07	0.93	Transition	Threonine→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.92
201C>T	0.14	0.86	Transition	Arginine→Threonine	Synonymous	0.83
203G>A	0.21	0.79	Transition	Arginine→Glycine	Non-synonymous	0.74
208C>T	0.31	0.69	Transition	Threonine→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.60
213A>G	0.24	0.76	Transition	Arginine→Valine	Synonymous	0.69
216C>T	0.34	0.65	Transition	Glutamic acid→Threonine	Synonymous	0.55
234C>T	0.34	0.65	Transition	Arginine→Threonine	Synonymous	0.65
240A>G	0.21	0.79	Transition	Serine→Valine	Synonymous	0.74
247C>T	0.34	0.65	Transition	Serine→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.55
252T>C	0.34	0.65	Transition	Arginine→Cysteine	Synonymous	0.55
272A>G	0.21	0.79	Transition	Tyrosine→Valine	Non-synonymous	0.74
301T>C	0.34	0.65	Transition	Proline→cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.55
321C>T	0.03	0.97	Transition	Asparagine→Cysteine	Synonymous	0.97
333A>G	0.21	0.79	Transition	Tyrosine→Alanine	Non-synonymous	0.74
346T>C	0.21	0.97	Transition	Leucine→Threonine	Synonymous	0.74
349A>G	0.10	0.90	Transition	Threonine→Valine	Non-synonymous	0.88
437T>C	0.34	0.65	Transition	Arginine→Cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.55
677A>G	0.45	0.55	Transition	Tyrosine→Alanine	Non-synonymous	0.43
Nn						
151T>C	0.36	0.64	Transition	Serine→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.53
183T>C	0.14	0.86	Transition	Arginine→Cysteine	Synonymous	0.83
194C>T	0.07	0.93	Transition	Arginine→Cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.92
196G>A	0.07	0.93	Transition	Glycine→Glycine	Non-synonymous	0.92
201C>T	0.36	0.64	Transition	Serine→Cysteine	Synonymous	0.53
206A>G	0.29	0.71	Transition	Serine→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.63
209C>T	0.36	0.64	Transition	Arginine→Alanine	Non-synonymous	0.53
227C>T	0.36	0.64	Transition	Isoleucine→Cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.53
233A>G	0.21	0.79	Transition	Serine→Valine	Non-synonymous	0.74
240C>T	0.36	0.64	Transition	Arginine→Cysteine	Synonymous	0.53
245T>C	0.36	0.64	Transition	Glutamine→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.53

	265A>G	0.21	0.79	Transition	Threonine→Valine	Non-synonymous	0.74
	294T>C	0.36	0.64	Transition	Tryptophan→Glycine	Synonymous	0.53
	314C>T	0.07	0.93	Transition	Histidine→Cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.92
	326A>G	0.21	0.79	Transition	Tyrosine→Valine	Non-synonymous	0.74
	339T>C	0.21	0.79	Transition	Glutamic acid→Threonine	Synonymous	0.74
	342A>G	0.07	0.93	Transition	Methionine→Valine	Synonymous	0.92
	430T>C	0.36	0.64	Transition	Leucine→Threonine	Synonymous	0.53
	670A>G	0.36	0.64	Transition	Alanine→Glycine	Non-synonymous	0.53
Ff	5A>T	0.07	0.93	Transversion	Methionine→Valine	Non-synonymous	0.92
	158T>C	0.14	0.86	Transition	Isoleucine→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	203G>A	0.14	0.86	Transition	Arginine→Glycine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	208C>T	0.14	0.86	Transition	Histidine→Cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	213A>G	0.14	0.86	Transition	Arginine→Alanine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	216C>T	0.14	0.86	Transition	Glutamic acid→Cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	234C>T	0.14	0.86	Transition	Arginine→Cysteine	Synonymous	0.83
	240A>G	0.14	0.86	Transition	Serine→Valine	Synonymous	0.83
	247C>T	0.14	0.86	Transition	Proline→Cysteine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	252T>C	0.14	0.86	Transition	Asparagine→Threonine	Synonymous	0.83
	272A>G	0.14	0.86	Transition	Tyrosine→Valine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	301T>C	0.14	0.86	Transition	Serine→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	333A>G	0.14	0.86	Transition	Glutamine→Arginine	Synonymous	0.83
	346T>C	0.14	0.86	Transition	Leucine→Threonine	Synonymous	0.83
	349A>G	0.14	0.86	Transition	Threonine→Valine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	437T>C	0.14	0.86	Transition	Glutamic acid→Threonine	Non-synonymous	0.83
	677G>A	0.29	0.71	Transition	Tyrosine→Glycine	Non-synonymous	0.63

G = Genotype

In naked neck chickens, variations in the number of major allele frequency was detected with lowest value of 0.64 observed in SNPs (151T>C, 201C>T, 209C>T, 227C>T, 240C>T, 245T>C, 294T>C, 430T>C and 670A>G), while highest value of 0.93 was seen in SNPs (194C>T, 196G>A, 314C>T and 342A>G). The estimates of heterozygosity in the chicken populations ranged from 0.07 in SNPs (194C>T, 196G>A, 314C>T and 342A>G) to 0.36 in SNPs (151T>C, 201C>T, 209C>T, 227C>T, 240C>T, 245T>C, 294T>C, 430T>C and 670A>G). Polymorphic information content (PIC) ranged from 0.53 in SNPs (151T>C, 201C>T, 209C>T, 227C>T, 240C>T, 245T>C, 294T>C, 430T>C and 670A>G) to 0.92 (194C>T, 196G>A, 314C>T and 342A>G). A total number of nineteen (19) SNPs were detected in

mtDNA D-loop of naked neck chickens. The naked neck had nineteen (19) transitions (151T>C, 183T>C, 194C>T, 196G>A, 201C>T, 206A>G, 209C>T, 227C>T, 233A>G, 240C>T, 245T>C, 265A>G, 294T>C, 314C>T, 326A>G, 339T>C, 342A>G, 430T>C and 670A>G) and no transversions. Majority of these SNPs had twelve (12) non-synonymous amino acid variations (151T>C, 194C>T, 196G>A, 206A>G, 209C>T, 227C>T, 233A>G, 245T>C, 265A>G, 314C>T, 326A>G and 670A>G), and seven (7) synonymous amino acid variations (183T>C, 201C>T, 240C>T, 294T>C, 339T>C, 342A>G and 430T>C).

In frizzle feathered chickens, variations was seen in the number of major allele frequency studies which ranged from the lowest value of 0.71 in SNPs (677G>A) to highest value of 0.93 in SNPs (5A>T). The estimates of heterozygosity in the chicken populations ranged from 0.07 in SNPs (5A>T) to 0.29 in SNPs (677G>A). Polymorphic information content (PIC) ranged from 0.63 in SNPs (677G>A) to 0.92 (5A>T). A total number of seventeen (17) SNPs were detected in mtDNA D-loop of frizzle feathered chickens. The frizzle feathered had sixteen (16) transitions (158T>C, 203G>A, 208C>T, 213A>G, 216C>T, 234C>T, 240A>G, 247C>T, 252T>C, 272A>G, 301T>C, 333A>G, 346T>C, 349A>G, 437T>C and 677G>A) and one (1) transversions (5A>T). Majority of these SNPs had twelve (12) non-synonymous amino acid

variations (5A>T, 158T>C, 203G>A, 208C>T, 213A>G, 216C>T, 247C>T, 272A>G, 301T>C, 349A>G, 437T>C and 677G>A), and five (5) synonymous amino acid variations (234C>T, 240A>G, 252T>C, 333A>G and 346T>C). Furthermore, majority of the SNPs observed were shared by normal feathered and frizzle feathered chickens with the exception of SNPs 190T>C, 201C>T and 321C>T.

The network analyses of mtDNA D-loop for three indigenous chicken populations are presented in Figure 1. Two haplogroup was observed in this study. Haplotypes 1, 4 and 6 together form different haplogroup with a well resolved distance from haplotype 2. Similarly, haplotypes 3 and 7 formed another haplogroup constituted isolated haplogroup off haplotype 2.

Figure 1: Network analysis of mtDNA D-loop for three indigenous chicken populations, the red colour between the haplotypes nodes refer to the positions of median vectors

Discussion

The result of the sequence analysis in this study showed presence of SNPs in normal feathered, naked neck and frizzle feathered chickens. These indicate presence of variability in these regions. The number of SNPs, transversions and transitions seen in the three indigenous chicken populations were not consistent with Ahmed et al. (2016) for genetic diversity of Hajar1 and Hajar2 local Saudi chicken line using mtDNA D-loop marker and Osman and Nishibori (2015) for

phylogenetic analysis of Egyptian native chickens based on mtDNA variations. The occurrence of 100% transitional mutation in naked neck chickens and 99% transitional mutation in normal and frizzle feathered chickens support the study on selective basis hypothesis of transition and transversion substitution which states that transition rates are much higher than expected by chance, relative to those of transversion inferring their biological significance by favoring natural

selection and overall relative fitness more than transversion (Pauly et al., 2017 and Lyons and Lauring, 2017). This result indicated that southwestern Nigeria indigenous chickens are highly polymorphic. Several authors have reported different polymorphisms in the gene with some of them associated with growth performance in broiler chickens (Dushyanth et al., 2016 and Zhang et al., 2019). Furthermore, the higher number of non-synonymous in the three indigenous chickens indicated that the mutation had significant effect on amino acid sequence and protein function. The high number of non-synonymous may cause a change in the type of protein formed which may probably influence growth and skeletal muscle development in the livestock. According to Chu and Wei (2019) non-synonymous mutations lead to amino acids changes and it changes protein structure and functions while synonymous mutations could not change the composition of peptide chain function. However, it is important in the translation process, which could alter the programmed translational velocity and the influence the encoded protein folding and function.

The allelic frequency shows the proportion or percentage of gene copies in a given population (Stephenson, 2016). The frequency of an allele ranges from 0 to 1. According to Aquadro (2001) where the frequency of an allele is 1, the population is said to be fixed for that particular allele. In this study the major allele frequency in normal feathered, naked neck and frizzle feathered range from 0.97 to 0.55, 0.93 to 0.64 and 0.93 to 0.71 respectively (Table 2). The evidence of high allelic frequency tending toward fixation suggests the presence of inbreeding in indigenous chickens studies. Heterozygosity quantifies within individual genetic diversity and is also related to inbreeding. Low heterozygosity detected across all the chickens in this study could be as a result of inbreeding or little genetic variability which could affect the fitness in natural setting

(Walling et al., 2011). This is an indicative of their potentials for genetic improvement via selection or crossbreeding. A similar result was reported by Durosaro et al. (2021).

The polymorphic information content (PIC) is a good indicator for the measurement of allele polymorphism. In measuring PIC, the loci is taken as highly polymorphic when PIC value is >0.5 ; it is taken as moderately polymorphic when PIC ranged from 0.25 to <0.5 and is taken as lowly polymorphic when PIC value is <0.25 (Botstein et al., 1980). The higher PIC generally observed in mtDNA D-loop of normal feathered, naked neck and frizzle feathered is an indication of genetic variation and selective potential using this maker for marker assisted selection (Andersson, 2001). Durosaro et al. (2021) also revealed similar finding. The implication is that the marker is highly informative for linkage studies of any of the genotypes chosen at random at this locus are likely to be heterozygous for this maker. The appearance of more than one haplogroup and more than one haplotype with a well resolving distance is an indication of genetic variability and multiple maternal lineages. This observation is somewhat a resemblance of the report on East African coast (Mwacharo et al., 2011) howbeit to a lesser extent. In the study of four country based on populations of village chicken, the researcher noted that the Kenyan populations exhibited greater haplotype and nucleotide diversities relative to the region. In addition, it was reported that Kenya had presence of two leading haplogroup (resulting to sub-structuring of that population) which they demonstrated to be of different maternal origins. Multiple maternal ancestries broadens genetic base of a population leading to greater genetic diversity (Silva et al., 2009). The observation for multiple maternal lineages agrees with Adebambo and chicken diversity consortium (2009) who reported multiple maternal origins for South Western Nigerian domestic chicken.

Fig 2: Normal feathered and naked neck

Fig 3: Frizzle feathered chicken

Conclusion and Recommendation

The present finding identified high mtDNA D-loop variation resulting from high mtDNA D-loop polymorphisms in Southwestern Nigeria indigenous chicken populations. This revealed high molecular differences within the indigenous chickens which could result to high adaptation to environmental changes under natural selection. Also, the PIC values observed was high suggesting that the marker is highly informative and may be suitable for linkage and genetic diversity study in Nigeria indigenous chicken populations. Furthermore, the population of indigenous chickens in this study showed low level of heterozygosity and as such may be homogenous in nature which is an indicative of their potentials for genetic improvement via selection or crossbreeding. Therefore, more detailed studies have to be conducted along with the appropriate breeding programs in order to maintain valuable genetics materials.

Ethical statement

I prioritize ethical conduct in all research endeavours, ensuring adherence to established guidelines, regulations and principles that protect human subjects, data and the integrity of the research process. The research did not include any individual person's data in any form and there are no competing interests.

The study was approved by the Department of Animal Breeding and Genetics, College of Animal Science and Livestock Production, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta, Ogun State.

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